

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF CANCER PROGRESSION AT ANGAU MEMORIAL PROVINCIAL HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT: The spread of cancer is still an important health concern in Papua New Guinea since it is becoming more common and causes deaths because of delay treatments, not enough testing, and a lack of treatment choices. In order to avoid this sickness of life to live longer, it is very important to avoid risk factors like smoking of tobacco, chewing of betel nuts, getting infected by bacteria and not complete treatment rates which includes cervical, breast, oral, vaginal, and kidney cancers. There are still important ways for early detection of a cancer patient, public awareness, or people's power despite recent developments, such as the spread of cancer with radiation treatment facilities or the new formation of cancer treatment inside health Department Programs in the Province.

Decreasing the way of drinking medication leads to common cancers including the breast, oral, or cervical tumors are often occurred because of not avoiding risk factors as illness becomes as common sickness for ordinary people. Such still remained as the common problems yet to be solved, especially in rural areas where access to health services is less due to transportation and roads, even though people are learning because of slow developments, yet the assessment, or treatments of tumor growth rate throughout Papua New Guinea

in particular has the outcome of both systematic health care limitations and growing weight for someone with cancer. Because according to the significant part of common habits of chewing of betel nut products, oral tumor rates stands-out among the as largest through the world, however cervical cancer also continue to be the main cause of most common cause of cancer-related deaths amongst many women in today's society.

This research is carried out to model the cancer progression in Angau Memorial Provincial Hospital using two equations, Gompertz modeling for dynamic tumor growth and (Two-compartments) for modeling. The key objectives of this research are basically to see how the two equations can be used to model the treatment response, cancer cell population and how the immune system respond to medication. nevertheless, some important options for improvements have been given by new programs including specialized screening measures and World Health Organization cancer protective measure and basically this research is carried out to predict whether there will be an increasing progression of cancer in the future leading to more death rates or there will be a decreasing case of cancer resulting in less death rates.

Keywords: *Gompertz modeling; Two-compartment modeling; tumor growth; immune system; cancer.*

Introduction

During the last 10 years, Papua New Guinea has experienced a shocking increase in both diagnoses of cancer and death rates, making cancers a major growing public health concern. Even though there are many other problems affecting the country, cancer has become increasingly recognized to be a quiet and terrified disease affecting individuals, families, and communities both in urban and rural areas. This has become difficult to correctly identify the magnitude of the disease given that late detection, shortage in availability of specialized treatment, plus a limited availability of accurate data from the cancer registry all impact the progression of cancer occurrence in Papua New Guinea. Table 1 (shows the radiotherapy Statistics).

In Papua New Guinea, some of the most common types of diseases that are currently affecting the people are diseases such as cervical, tumors of breast, oral, and the

linear tumor. Our country is a country wherein a larger number of overall patients have nearly doubled in recent years, based on present health statistics. Because especially substantial part to less detection availability and poor HPV vaccination rates, cervical cancer in particular remains as the top tier which contributes as the leading cause of death from cancer amongst women. Many individuals come during the last stages of their medical condition, which they have fewer effective options for treatment and significantly smaller timeframe of survival. Poor public awareness, social stigma, and geographical barriers which blocks quick accessibility to healthcare services are often the major reasons for the delay diagnosis to occur.

The medical issues in the country is seriously constrained in its capacity to deal with the increasing rate of cancers. The Angau Memorial Provincial Hospital in Lae serves as the most common cancer therapy center, which found it challenging as times to take in victims from all over the nation. Drugs/medicines for chemotherapy are often in less supply, radiation facilities are limited, and specialized oncologist specialists are very hard to find across. These constraints contribute to significant deaths and prolonged suffering for patients. Table 2 & 3 (Shows the treatment summary)

There are several plans which are recommended and are underway to prevent the spread of the disease throughout Papua New Guinea. These include health workers go out making public health awareness, pilot testing programs, and partnerships with international health agencies. More or less, this is challenging to develop targeted approaches with the lack of a national cancer registry because reliable information about cases, death rate, and lifespan remain very difficult to get through. To Change the present pattern, it requires improving and supporting early identification programs, improving therapy effectiveness, and strengthening public health schooling (Azizi, 2024).

Literature review

Cancer progression is basically talking about the changes that occurs inside and outside the human body that causes changes to the physicality of body like losing weight, losing hair, and shard pain from inside of the body, skin or eyes turning

yellow and many more. These are the physical symptoms of the body if one individual overcomes this, he or she must go to a medical health center and get tested to know the type of cancer they are likely to have. Cancer progression is normally described through tumor stage at diagnosis.

In the past the system, of cancer diagnosis is carried through clinical pathology from the study of macroscopic organ and tissue changes at autopsies. In 1996 doctor Leonhard Mullauer carried out the research of cancer progression in France using the clinical pathology. He found out that the molecular pathological determination of solid tumors is HER2 implication in breast carcinoma, KRAS mutation in colorectal cancer and EGFR mutation in lung adenocarcinoma. He basically used the ordinary derivative equation to determine the solid tumors like HER2 breast carcinoma and the other three symptoms mention above.

Today in Papua New Guinea, technology is advancing so our doctors now used the radiotherapy and chromatography to diagnosis a patient. These two methods are used to extract variables such as demographics (age, sex), cancer type and histology, date of diagnosis, stage at diagnosis, treatment received, and outcome and performance status. The two mathematical modeling equations that are commonly used today to model cancer progressions are Gompertz modeling and Two-compartment modeling. They are used because they gave a clear outcome of how fast or slow the cancer will spread.

After digging up some histories of mathematical modeling made in the past and compared it with today's modeling. We can basically see that, in the past they used old equipment's and some results were not accurate, not enough medicine and some results are can only determine one type of cancer and others were hidden which results in more deaths. Today the technology is advancing so when a patient went for a cancer test. They can easily identify which type of cancer and at which stage so correct treatment can be applied to save the person's life.

However, despite the general availability of Angau's cancer progression equipment's. There are three basic areas in need of research and they are, the lack of Angau-specific document on progression patterns, insufficient understanding of system-level

contributors to progression in Papua New Guinea and Limited comparative evidence between Angau and other regional hospitals.

Key Highlights:

- Total Cancer Cases Registered: 252 (September: 66, October: 76, November: 72, December: 38)
- Common Cancer Types: Cervical, Head and Neck, Breast.
- Gender Distribution: Females accounted for 68.7%, and males for 31.3%.
- Geographical Distribution: Most cases originated from Morobe Province (41.2%), followed by Highlands and Momase regions.

Risk Factors: Betelnut chewing, smoking, and alcohol consumption were prominent Contributor.

Table 1: External Beam Radiotherapy Statistics: 2010-2016

Year	New Case	Head & Neck	Cervix	Breast	Others	Total Patients	Fields	Remarks
2010	109	29	47	13	20	788	3025	July
2011	251	65	110	24	52	2472	8119	March
2012	186	36	77	21	34	1533	6041	August
2013	251	67	79	22	43	1476	6545	May
2014	168	55	78	17	18	1166	6545	June
2015	248	129	73	23	23	2818	9250	June
2016	225	95	73	16	41	2998	11467	April

The table above is the current external beam radiotherapy statistics collected from Angau Memorial Provincial Hospital. The statistics given collective tallies of head & neck, cervix, breast and other cancers from 2010-2016.

Table 2: Radiotherapy treatment for 2024

MONTHS	NEW PATIENTS	ONGOING	COMPLETED	TOTAL Rx
September	37	33	17	1710
October	35	41	20	1632
November	30	38	15	1450
December	1	52	45	1165
Total	103	164	97	5957

The table above is basically the radiotherapy treatment for 2024. It shows the number of new patients, the number ongoing patients and the number of patients with completed treatments with its total from the month of September to December.

Table 3: Chemotherapy treatment for 2024

MONTHS	NEW PATIENTS	ONGOING	TOTAL PATIENTS	
September	10	43	53	
October	12	59	71	
November	14	63	77	
December	12	59	71	
Total	48	224	272	

The table above shows the chemotherapy treatment for 2024. It shows the number of new patients, the number of ongoing patients and the number of patients with completed treatments with its total from September to December.

Mortality and Survival:

- Total Deaths: 20
- Head & Neck: 7
- Breast: 3
- Cervix: 6
- Others: 4

Materials

Modeling tumor dynamic growth of cancer progression using Gompertz model

Let's denote:

$$t = \text{time (months)}$$

$$N(t) = \text{growth size}$$

The Gompertz model is widely used in cancer modeling because it captures:

Fast initial growth

Slowing growth due to biological constraints

Differential Equation

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = rN\left(1 - \frac{N}{K}\right)$$

Where:

N (t): growth size

r: growth rate constant

K: carrying capacity

Applying to Angau Data

Let's define:

t = [0, 1, 2, 3] → Sept–Dec

N (t) = Ongoing patients = [33, 41, 38, 52]

So, the model becomes:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = rN\left(1 - \frac{N}{K}\right)$$

With:

Initial condition: N (0) = 33

Methodology

This study was carried out at Angau Memorial Provincial Hospital (MoPH) to look into the development of cancer in three major areas: Tumor cell population (how tumor characteristics and burden may change over visits and treatment), tumor dynamic growth (how tumor burden changes over time), and immune response to cancer (how host immune activity is represented in clinics and easy to access diagnostics tests).

The current data on cancer progression from 2010 to 2016 is shown above. The cancer data collection can be collected from health workers in several ways; below are some ways the data was taken from different records at Angau General hospital and they are mainly collected from:

- Diagnostic records
- Files for patients
- Standard review registry
- Standard chemistry lab
- Admission
- Discharge registries

After collecting the data, two mathematical equations were used and they are the Gompertz model and Two-compartment model because they are both perfectly fits for mathematical modelling. Gompertz modeling is basically used to represent nonlinear cancer progression which shows how progression rate changes from time to time whereas two-compartment modeling is basically used to represent cancer progression in two stages like:

- Fast cancer progression
- Slow cancer progression

Few assumptions were made by applying the two mathematical modeling equations, such as that the two models describe the primary structure where they represent the key elements of time and its outcomes. The timing of the clinical process is shown in the review period of patients, and two patients with different types of cancer do not impact one another.

Results

By applying the Gompertz modeling for dynamic tumor growth with the data collected for radiotherapy at Angau. We can see that the red circles represent the actual data points and the blue curves represent the Gompertz model fit. The tumor growth is nonlinear and tumor progression is under treatment from September down to December where the treatment is delay with slow progress. We can also see that

suitability of Gompertz dynamics for modeling treatment response well than the not treated tumor rate of expansion.

We also use the model structure (Two-compartments) for modeling Tumor (cancer) cell population and Immune response (or effective treatment response) where we found out that if the Immune system and Tumor cells respond to treatments then we say the treatment is effective which means it's working. If one only responds to treatments and the other did not than the treatment is not effective. According to its MATLAB graph, we can say that the month of December shows stronger immune system responded to cancer and improves its therapy efficiency.

Discussion

The results we get by applying the Gompertz growth model to the radiotherapy data collected from Angau shows that the model provides a reasonable estimation of tumor dynamics under treatment conditions. The current data points represented by red circles closely follow the fitted Gompertz curves (blue lines), indicating that the model is capable of capturing the overall nonlinear behavior of tumor progression and regression from time to time.

The tumor growth pattern is clearly nonlinear, which runs close with the main expectations, as tumor expansion typically slows as it shows up physically or the condition of treatments. From September down to December, the data suggest or shows a very period of active treatment, it shows the tumor size can be reduced or controlled if patients continue to take medical treatment faithfully. However, the observed results or delay in treatment response around December highlights a possible disruption or reduction in treatment effectiveness, which is shown in the change of trend of the fitted curve.

These findings support the idea of using the Gompertz model for representing tumor dynamics under radiotherapy. Unlike the model done by Tahmineh Azizi from Biology Department, University of Missouri-St. Louis, St. Louis, MO 63121, USA; tanh8@umsl.edu

Where his findings were about modeling of tumor growth patterns and their response to treatment methods.

In addition, the two-compartment model combining both tumor cell population and immune or treatment response provides further knowledge into the treatment effectiveness. It also shows that within this framework; the treatment effectiveness can be interpreted as a coupled response between loss of tumor function and activation of immune system. The results suggest that when both compartments respond to treatment, the therapy can be considered effective. On the other hand, if only one component responds while the other remains unaffected, the overall treatment effectiveness is reduced.

Based on the MATLAB graphing results, the time around December indicates a stronger immune response or improved the treatment success, as from the evidence by a more significant change in tumor dynamics. This may suggest whether it is an adaptive immune activation or an improved response to radiotherapy during that time. Overall, the combined modeling idea shows the importance of combining both tumor kinetics and immune dynamics to clearly understand and carry out radiotherapy outcomes.

Figures

MATLAB Graph for the ongoing patients from September to December in 2024

Figure 1. The graph above shows the nonlinear growth of the ongoing patients of 2024, starting from September to December. The spikes basically indicate treatment queue whether it can be a fast progression or slow progression.

Model Structure (Two Compartments)

We define two interacting populations:

T (t): cancer growth

I (t): Immune response

A standard two-compartment tumor-immune model is:

$$\text{i. } \frac{dT}{dt} = rT(1 - T/K) - \alpha TI$$

$$\text{ii. } \frac{dI}{dt} = s + \beta TI - dI$$

Word equation interpretation

r: tumor growth rate

K: carrying capacity

α : immune killing rate

s: baseline immune activation

β : immune stimulation by growth presence

d: immune decay rate

Table 4: Linking Two-compartment model to the radiotherapy for 2024

Month	New	Ongoing	Completed	Total Rx
September	37	33	17	1710
October	35	41	20	1632
November	30	38	15	1450
December	1	52	45	1165

Figure 5.3: Shows how data from the radiotherapy test from 2024 is link with Two-compartment model equations for modeling graphs given below.

T (t) \approx Ongoing + New patient's \rightarrow growth size

I (t) \approx Completed cases \rightarrow treatment success

Table 5: Model calculation

Month	(T)	(I)
September	70	17
October	76	20
November	68	15
December	53	45

Figure 4: Shows the modeling of ongoing, new and completed cases of radiotherapy treatment from 2024. The modeling highlights that growth sizes increase, immune response increases significantly in December.

Modeling the data using graph

Month's treatments

Time = 0,1,2,3

Initial conditions: $T(0) = 70$ $I(0) = 17$

MATLAB Graph for the month of September 2024

Figure 2: The graph above illustrates how an increasingly strong immune system reacts to drugs, increases the effectiveness of therapy, and slows the growth of cancer. On the other hand, a weakened immune system makes tumor cells more likely to spread and does not react to medication. The graph is only for the month of September 2024.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the application of the Gompertz growth model to the radiotherapy dataset from Angau effectively shows its ability to describe tumor dynamics under treatment. The close agreement between the observed data and the fitted model confirms that tumor progression and regression follow a nonlinear pattern that is well captured by the Gompertz formulation, particularly in a clinical setting involving radiotherapy.

The theory further shows that tumor growth is influenced by treatment from time to time, with evidence of tumor suppression from September to December and a possible difference in treatment response towards December. This highlights the usefulness of model in identifying changes in treatment effectiveness and tumor behavior from time to time.

In addition, the inclusion of the two-compartment model, representing both tumor cells and immune or treatment response, provides additional knowledge of therapy effectiveness. The results indicate that effective treatment is associated with an organized response between tumor suppression and immune activation, whereas the inequality between these responses may indicate reduced medical efficiency.

Overall, the findings confirm that combining the Gompertz model with a two-compartment structure offers a more comprehensive understanding of tumor dynamics under radiotherapy. This comprehensive approach improves the ability to conduct treatment effectiveness and may support improved clinical decision-making in cancer therapy interview.

Based on the research that was done. The implementation of standard cancer registration forms, the use of standard criteria for initial staging, treatment plans, and progression results, and assurance of correct date recording are some suggestions proposed to improve cancer data collection going forward in future. Angau Memorial Provincial Hospital should develop a reviewed schedule with timing measurements appropriate for the type of cancer, record the treatment response using standard criteria, and clearly track treatment records and side effects in order to effectively monitor cancer treatment. Implementing a straightforward or safety of medical data

with regular data audits will improve accuracy, conduct continuous model-based assessment of treatment effectiveness, and allow appropriate upgrading of therapy when progression is indicated (Sanga, et al., 2006).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is not conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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